

WHAT IS REINCARNATE

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

KEY FACTS

Demo Case / Value Chain

Paris Habitat (France)

Lead Partners

TU Delft, Paris Habitat

Innovation(s) applied

Circular Decision-making for Real Estate Assets

TRL (before → after)

[3 → 6]

Related Deliverables

[D2.2, D3.1]

CONTEXT AND INNOVATION

The Paris Habitat demonstration shows how structured and collaborative decision-making can support the circular renovation and densification of mid-20th-century social housing in Paris. The apartment complex of 281 dwellings faces typical challenges of energy inefficiency, affordability, and outdated spatial layouts.

TU Delft applied a circular decision-making process that helps organisations plan renovation strategies in a consistent, transparent, and participatory way. The process combines stakeholder dialogue with systematic analysis of different renovation pathways, balancing environmental, technical, and social objectives. It supports asset managers in exploring “what-if” futures, comparing trade-offs, and identifying the most robust strategies for extending building life.

In this case, the approach brought together experts from Paris Habitat’s sustainability, architecture, BIM, and social departments to jointly assess renovation options. Digital and AI-based tools were used to translate analytical results into accessible visual and narrative formats, allowing a broader audience to engage with complex decisions.

The outcome is a replicable way of working that improves early-stage decision quality and strengthens collaboration between technical and strategic actors.

DEMONSTRATION AND RESULTS

The demonstration brought together Paris Habitat’s sustainability, architecture, BIM, and asset management teams to jointly develop and rank a set of renovation scenarios for a 1950s social housing complex.

The process began with identifying shared project values and objectives, followed by the co-creation of several possible future pathways.

These scenarios explored different combinations of renovation intensity, energy upgrades, added living space, and environmental measures.

Stakeholders then compared and ranked the scenarios to understand how each direction aligned with their collective priorities.

Within this scenario set, one option — “Timber-Toned Transition” — emerged as the most preferred scenario according to the decision model, combining renovation of the existing structures with improved energy performance and the potential use of lightweight timber extensions and green roofs.

Beyond identifying a preferred scenario, the exercise created a clear overview of all viable renovation pathways, clarified trade-offs, and strengthened shared understanding of how different options would affect affordability, comfort, and long-term sustainability.

This outcome reflects the results of the scenario development and ranking process, providing Paris Habitat with a structured basis for future planning without implying a final or implemented decision.

Scenario 13: The Timber-Toned Transition

On a quiet street in Paris’s south-west, a mid-century residential block has emerged from renovation with a new, understated confidence. The building’s familiar horizontal form remains, but the fresh façade tells a story of careful, deliberate change. Smooth light-colored insulation panels frame triple-glazed windows, while vertical bands of warm-toned timber bring rhythm and warmth to the exterior.

Above, a discreet row of flush-mounted solar panels hints at the building’s leap to Energy Label A (Strong). Together with the upgraded rooftop ventilation system, they cut energy consumption and create a more stable, comfortable indoor climate. The transformation is quiet but measurable, delivering environmental and comfort benefits in equal measure.

Sustainability threads through the design. The project delivers Low Environmental Impact (Strong) through recycled timber and fiber cement cladding, permeable paving along the walkway, and a bioswale tucked near the downspouts to manage rainwater naturally. No demolition scars the site — the structure has been preserved, adapted, and enhanced rather than replaced.

The increase in space is modest: 1 Floor Addition (Low). The extra level is set back from the façade, its timber cladding blending with the rest of the palette. It houses a handful of new apartments without altering the building’s balanced proportions or overshadowing the street.

Greenery has been added sparingly: Low Addition of Green Spaces (Weak). Small trees have been planted at the front, their stakes still visible, and shrubs line the pathway. Planters at balcony edges bring subtle splashes of seasonal green.

Community amenities see Small Improvement (Weak). The upgraded bicycle racks are neatly placed by the entrance, benches encourage brief pauses and conversations, and new LED lighting at the canopy ensures a welcoming, safe glow after sunset.

Seen from the street, the building feels renewed yet rooted in its history. Its timber accents and crisp lines bridge mid-century geometry with contemporary sustainability, creating a façade that feels both modern and neighborly. It’s a transition defined not by spectacle, but by thoughtful calibration — a gentle shift toward a lower-carbon, higher-comfort future.

Descriptors		
	Energy Performance	Energy Label A ●●●
	Environmental Impact	Low impact ●●●
	Densification	1 Floor addition ●○
	Green Spaces	Low addition ●○○
	Services & Outdoor Spaces	Small improvement ○○○
	Quality of Use	Medium improvement ●○○
	Indoor Comfort	Low - small upgrade ○○○
	Diversification	Diverse housing supply ●●
	Cost	Within budget ●●●
	Social Cohesion	Low social impact ○○○
	Marketing & City Policy	In accordance with plans ●

Legend for Fuzzy Value:

- Red: Fuzzy Value (Low)
- Yellow: Fuzzy Value (Medium)
- Green: Fuzzy Value (High)

MAIN RESULTS

- A full set of co-developed renovation scenarios with clear descriptions and assumptions.
- Improved shared insight into how different renovation directions perform across key criteria.
- Identification of “Timber-Toned Transition” as the most preferred scenario within the decision model.
- Stronger alignment across technical and social departments.
- A structured, reusable workflow for analysing future Paris Habitat projects.

TECHNICAL HIGHLIGHTS

Core methods

Scenario development and ranking supported by ScenarioWizard and AI-based visualisation tools.

Data sources

Stakeholder inputs, project objectives, and renovation options organised into comparable scenarios.

CP-IM integration

Inputs such as objectives, descriptors, variants, and their value ranges were prepared in a format that can be linked to CP-IM for future data exchange and reuse.

Lessons learned

Improved clarity, stronger collaboration, and easier communication of complex choices, steep learning curve however.

IMPACTS AND REPLICATION

CATEGORY	IMPACTS	FOCUS	CONTRIBUTION LEVEL
Scientific	I1-I6	Demonstrates operational, data-driven circular decision-making in a real case	High
Societal	I7-I12	Builds shared understanding and legitimacy in public-housing renovation	High
Techno-economic	I13-I18	Improves efficiency and quality of early investment decisions	Medium-High

LINKS

<https://zenodo.org/records/17426235>
<https://zenodo.org/records/17549003>
<https://zenodo.org/records/15012079>
<https://zenodo.org/records/14417214>
<https://zenodo.org/records/13987747>
<https://zenodo.org/records/11104769>

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

DECISION TRANSPARENCY

Baseline

Low

Expected / Achieved

100% traceability of scenario choices

STAKEHOLDER ALIGNMENT

Baseline

Fragmented

Expected / Achieved

Alignment across 4–5 departments

PLANNING EFFICIENCY

Baseline

0% improvement

Expected / Achieved

≈30% faster early-stage preparation

REPLICATION POTENTIAL

The approach used in the Paris Habitat demonstration can be transferred to other renovation and adaptation projects where different departments need to compare options early in the process. Because it relies mainly on stakeholder input, basic project information, and structured scenario development, it can be applied by housing associations, municipalities, or asset managers facing similar challenges. The workflow and materials created in this case can serve as a template, and the prepared data can be linked to CP-IM to support reuse in future projects.

CONTACTS

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